

Heart rate variability in patients with severe traumatic brain injury undergoing early orthostatic exercise – Short statistical analysis plan.

Authors: Markus Harboe Olsen, Christian Riberholt

Contributors: Michala Schultz, Ronan M. G. Berg, Jesper Mehlsen, Kirsten Møller

Date: 03.01.2022 (dd.mm.yy)

Clinicaltrials.gov registration: NCT02924649

Ethical registration: Scientific-Ethics Committee of the Capital Region in Denmark (H-16041794)

Introduction

Control of cardiovascular function may be compromised in the early phase after TBI.

Aim of the study

Our primary aim is to describe short-term heart rate variability in the supine and upright positions in patients with TBI before any intervention was applied.

Our secondary aim is to describe long-term heart rate variability in the same patient groups from up to 5 days of Holter-monitoring. In both instances we will compare a group that received tilt training to one receiving usual care.

Methods

The study data was gathered alongside the data for a trial investigating the feasibility and safety of early orthostatic exercises in patients with severe traumatic brain injury [2, 3]. The study was conducted following the latest version of the Helsinki Declaration [4] and the ICMJE Recommendations for the Protection of Research Participants (www.icmje.org). The study protocol was published [2], approved by the Scientific-Ethics Committee of the Capital Region in Denmark (H-16041794), and registered at ClinicalTrials.gov (NCT02924649). As the data collected for the analysis of heart rate variability are meant to generate hypotheses, we have added several heart rate variability indices to derive a better understanding of this aspect in the physiology during head-up tilt (see below “*Analysis of data*”).

Participants

38 patients were included on average 12.8 (SD 5.2) days after having a traumatic brain injury (Table 1). Patients included had a Glasgow Coma Score (GCS) lower than 11, with suspected persistent disorders of consciousness, and a stable intracranial pressure (< 20 mmHg) for 24 hours. Patients were excluded if they had spinal cord injuries or fractures of the lower extremities that prohibited weightbearing were excluded, or in case of lack of consent from the nearest relative.

Randomization and masking

Patients were randomly assigned (1:1) to four weeks of either early orthostatic exercise (intervention group) or standard care (control), using a web-based computer-generated block-randomization procedure. Block sizes were randomly assigned as either 4, 6, or 8 patients in each block. We stratified the randomization according to either low or high GCS (3-6 and 7-10, respectively). Due to the nature of the intervention (tilt-table), it was not possible to mask the intervention to the clinical staff or the patient.

Intervention and standard care

The early orthostatic exercise consisted of daily (weekdays) head-up tilt on an ERIGO® tilt-table (Hocoma, Switzerland) to 70 degrees tilt for 20 minutes. In case of a critical reduction in either blood pressure or cerebral perfusion pressure, or an increase in intracranial pressure, or heart rate as described above, the patient was moved to 0 degrees until stable and then returned to standing [2]. Time at 0 degrees was not considered part of the 20-minute session. Patients who regained the ability to stand up during the four-week intervention period did not undergo further orthostatic exercise but remained in the study.

Treatment in the standard care group was decided by the treating physician, nurses, and therapists. Mobilization could be a part of the standard care but occurred at a much smaller scale than in the intervention group; the major focus of standard care was respiratory optimization and re-positioning to prevent pressure ulcers.

Measurements

Two types of electrocardiography (ECG) devices were used. At baseline patients were equipped with a device for measuring two-lead ECG (ePatch - Biotelemetry, Inc. Malvern, United States). The ePatch is placed with an adhesive tape over the sternum and records continuous ECG for up to five days (120 hours) at a sample rate of 256 Hz. Immediately after the five days, data was secured on a local hard drive for later analysis.

For measurement during the tilt-table test at baseline, two-weeks, and four-weeks a three-lead ECG was recorded using a bio-amplifier (FE132 Bio Amp, ADInstruments, Oxford, UK) before and during head-up tilt at a sample rate of 1 kHz. The data from the device were stored using Labchart (Labchart ver 8.0, ADInstruments, Oxford, UK). We chose this measurement to obtain data that were synchronised with the head-up tilt procedure.

Analysis of data

The stored data were assessed in Kubios HRV Premium version 3.4.3 (Kubios Oy, Kuopio, Finland). The five days continuous recordings were checked for artefacts using an automatic beat detection in the Kubios software [5]. In 24-hour intervals, the successive heart beats were used to analyse the RR-intervals taken from the QRS complex of the ECG.

For analyses of the recordings obtained during head-up tilt, the data were divided in two five-minutes intervals providing a five-minutes supine measure and a five-minutes head-up tilt measure. The measurements were visually inspected for artefacts and spurious peaks were removed from the analysis.

We will analyse the following HRV variables [6–8]: In the frequency domain - low frequency (LF – 0.04 to 0.15 Hz), high frequency (HF – 0.15 to 0.40 Hz) and the ratio between LF and HF, and total power; in the time domain - standard deviations of successive RR intervals (SDNN) and root mean square of successive

RR intervals differences (RMSSD); in non-linear parameters -sample entropy as a quantification of total irregularity and detrended fluctuations analysis (DFA1).

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis will be done by two independent investigators using either SAS/STAT software (SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC, USA) and latest stable version of R (R Core Team, Vienna, Austria).

All data will be presented as mean and standard deviation if a normal distribution can be assumed, if this is not the case, we will use median and interquartile range. Dichotomous demographic data will be presented as number and percentage.

As multiple outcomes are more likely to show a spurious low p -value we will adjust the alpha level of the primary outcome and secondary outcome using the method suggested by Jakobsen et al. [9]. By dividing the original alpha level with the number between no correction (1) and the Bonferroni correction (in this case 6) a p -value below 0.016 will be accepted as significant. The most conservative p -value will be chosen if there are differences in the two independent analyses due to software specific variation not caused by differences in the chosen statistical methods.

For the primary outcome the difference between HRV in five-minute intervals will be analysed at baseline before and during head-up tilt using paired t -test or Wilcoxon signed rank test as the equivalent non-parametric test.

Secondarily, we will analyse data using the five-day ECG monitoring. The 24 hours measurement for the first three days will be analysed using a mixed effects model with intervention group and time as fixed effects and participants as random effect. Both groups receive similar intervention at day 1, while they only differ from day two onwards. Therefore, all participants will be coded as in control group at day one, and for day two and onwards they will be coded according to their respective group. The mixed effect model will investigate if there is group specific differences over time.

Two independent investigators will analyse the data and compare the statistical reports. If large deviations occur a third report will be generated. After publication of the study all reports will be uploaded in a public repository.

It should be noted that the results should be interpreted as hypothesis generating regardless of the level of significance. Therefore, a power calculation estimated on the collected data will be suggested as a supplement.

The non-linear parameters will be presented graphically using both the 5 minutes and 24-hour data.

References

1. Lloyd-Donald P, Spencer W, Cheng J, Romero L, Jithoo R, Udy A, et al. In adult patients with severe traumatic brain injury, does the use of norepinephrine for augmenting cerebral perfusion pressure improve neurological outcome? A systematic review. *Injury*. 2020;51:2129–34.
2. Riberholt CG, Lindschou J, Gluud C, Mehlsen J, Møller K. Early mobilisation by head-up tilt with stepping versus standard care after severe traumatic brain injury – Protocol for a randomised clinical feasibility trial. *Trials*. 2018;19:612. doi:10.1186/s13063-018-3004-x.
3. Riberholt CG, Olsen MH, Søndergaard CB, Gluud C, Ovesen C, Jakobsen JC, et al. Early Orthostatic Exercise by Head-Up Tilt With Stepping vs. Standard Care After Severe Traumatic Brain Injury Is Feasible. *Front Neurol*. 2021;1:626014. doi:10.3389/fneur.2021.626014.
4. World Medical Association declaration of Helsinki: Ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects. *JAMA*. 2013;310:2191–4.
5. Lipponen JA, Tarvainen MP. A robust algorithm for heart rate variability time series artefact correction using novel beat classification. *J Med Eng Technol*. 2019;43:173–81. doi:10.1080/03091902.2019.1640306.
6. Kleiger RE, Stein PK, Bigger JT. Heart rate variability: Measurement and clinical utility. *Annals of Noninvasive Electrocardiology*. 2005;10:88–101. doi:10.1111/j.1542-474X.2005.10101.x.
7. Henriques T, Ribeiro M, Teixeira A, Castro L, Antunes L, Costa-Santos C. Nonlinear methods most applied to heart-rate time series: A review. *Entropy*. 2020;22. doi:10.3390/e22030309.
8. Malik M, Camm AJ, Bigger JT, Breithardt G, Cerutti S, Cohen RJ, et al. Heart rate variability. Standards of measurement, physiological interpretation, and clinical use. *European Heart Journal*. 1996;17:354–81.
9. Jakobsen JC, Wetterslev J, Winkel P, Lange T, Gluud C. Thresholds for statistical and clinical significance in systematic reviews with meta-analytic methods. *BMC Med Res Methodol*. 2014;14.